

FORMATION OF PSYCHOLOGICAL THINKING IN THE STUDY OF LATIN LANGUAGE IN MEDICAL HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

Sabirova Sabina Olimovna

Asian International University

Assistant Professor, Department of "Fundamental Medicine"

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the development of psychological thinking of medical students and the methods of using various concepts in teaching Latin.

The rapid development of the medical field in the world has further increased the need for teaching Latin. It is important to conduct scientific research on the development of abstract grammatical thinking in online open distance courses, taking into account the development of linguistic thinking in students of medical higher education institutions, to formulate grammatical forms and categories of the Latin language taught on the basis of ancient culture. Today, the educational and methodological support of in-depth teaching of Latin in medical higher education institutions is of particular importance. In this regard, the need to modernize the methodological support of teaching Latin in medical higher education institutions on the basis of a competency-based approach, to improve the didactic foundations of intellectual and cultural development of students on the basis of fundamental and practical knowledge on the principle of concentration, and to clarify the taxonomy of systematizing educational materials of an intellectual and cultural nature is explained.

At the beginning of the 20th century, F. Zelinsky created a set of lectures aimed at substantiating the necessity for modern society of studying the culture of antiquity, including the Latin language. He emphasized that the teaching of Latin at various stages, despite its connection with that era, should always be aimed at enriching the intellect and culture.

According to N. Katsman, teaching Latin in higher education institutions allows students to form linguistic worldviews, develop abstract grammatical thinking, establish a scientific approach to the study of their native language and foreign languages, and develop general cultural and intellectual competence in students through the study of ancient culture. The student's mastery of the grammar and vocabulary necessary for reading Latin texts with the help of a dictionary allows him to improve his professional competence.

A. Podosinov emphasized that the main goal of teaching Latin is to form an individual educational strategy, and concluded that this open-ended and relatively easily mastered

language system creates a visual and convenient idea of organizing language learning in general and allows for a conscious approach to learning any language in the world.

In teaching Latin, directing students to find independent solutions to various problem situations is of greater importance than simply mastering specialized knowledge. These skills will allow the student to search for and process the necessary information in the future, understand the essence of the issue, make the right decision, as well as acquaint students of medical higher educational institutions with the moral, political, and aesthetic values developed by the ancient Greeks and Romans, educate a citizen with a firm life position and a responsible attitude to his personal activities. Enriching students' thinking based on analyzing the form and meaning of words in Latin, as well as studying the structure of words in a synchronous mode, develops students' analytical thinking and requires the classification of language forms, borrowed, archaic words, and neologisms. Teaching Latin, which reflects the rich heritage of science and culture of ancient states, provides an opportunity to identify important aspects such as the intellectual and cultural development of students and their training in active independent research; the ancient foundations of the Latin language; deepening students' thinking processes through the analysis of the form and meaning of words; studying loanwords, comparing them with other languages; the difficulty and complexity of mastering classical grammatical forms, analytical thinking, analyzing archaisms and loanwords; understanding the influence of the laws of Latin grammar on other languages. In the process of studying Latin, various types and forms of speech are mastered as an important component of the intellectual and cultural development of students. In particular, the task of convenient perception of the material through external (oral) speech through deep processing of the text; mastering the mnemonic description of the dialogue between the writer and the reader for written speech is solved. Dialogic speech requires the ability to understand the interlocutor's thoughts and respond appropriately. Monologue speech, as a complex type of speech activity, requires deep insight into the essence of the issue and the development of oratory skills.

Each student can choose one or more concepts of medicine or pharmacology according to their interests, offer alternative ideas on the main selected concepts proposed by the teacher, their own options for classifying the studied and translated sentences; using a textbook, manual, dictionary, identify several explanations related to one concept, translate sentences into Uzbek, actively using the knowledge gained in grammar and lexicology; clarify the Uzbek equivalent of the selected concepts; discuss and analyze the main concepts in the discussion process; analyze the expression of the medical concept in Russian and English and present it in the form of a cluster.

In the course of educational experimental work, a system of practical exercises was redeveloped and put into practice on the topics "Introduction to the Latin language and medical terminology. Latin alphabet. Vowels and consonants. Diphthongs and digraphs. Body structure". The following technological algorithm was used to organize and conduct the practical training: Motivational stage. Read the words given under the numbers below correctly and fill in the "Analysis of Concepts" table:

1) cancer, medicamentum, auris, abortus, articulatio, lingua; 2) ventriculus, ren, oculus, sanguis, pectus, thorax; 3) corpus, dens, fel, epiphysis, caries, oesophagus; 4) hemispherium, ichthyismus, thrombus, scarlatina, angulus, olfactu; 5) intestinum, incisura, rhinitis, series,

aqua, pharmacon; 6) oedema, musculus, vena, cytoplasma, defectus, dolorrabies; 7) sutura, causa, medicus, cellula, os; 8) curatio, visus, homo, lapis, cutis, abductor; 9) diaphysis, processus, sulcus, scabies, epicondylus, fascia; 10) punctum, insertio, ictus, cranium, epithelium, cavum; 11) encephalon, colon, metacarpus, bacterium, plexus, vitium; 12) rubeola, exophthalmia, diphtheria, migraena, costa, tactus.

Clarify the goals and objectives of the lesson based on the "Goal" technique. The following goals and objectives of the lesson were clarified in collaboration with the students: to enumerate and describe the main structural units of the body; to describe the anatomical position of the body; to determine the location of body cavities and abdominal-pelvic areas; to define terms related to the position, orientation and surfaces of the body and to use them during X-ray examination; to describe common signs, symptoms and diseases that can affect certain body systems; to describe common diagnostic, conservative and surgical procedures related to certain body systems; to recognize, define, correctly pronounce and write terms; to apply knowledge in practice by successfully completing assignments.

In teaching Latin, the following goals and objectives of the lesson were identified: to organize the process of working with concepts and realities for students, in accordance with their interests, students should choose one or more concepts of medicine or pharmacology; The teacher suggests alternative ideas for the main selected concepts, their own options for classifying the studied and translated sentences; using a textbook, manual, dictionary, to identify several explanations related to one concept; to clarify the Uzbek equivalent of the selected concepts; to analyze the expression of the medical concept in Russian and English and to present it in the form of clusters.

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